

MEMORY (RE)PRODUCED

ykks and darzanà

Deniz Dilan Kara, Ece Ünübol, Dide Dinç

TEGET Architecture

In an atmosphere of urban amnesia in Istanbul, Teğet aims to uncover and (re) produce memory through two projects.

YKKS was re-built within the imaginary, if not physical, boundaries of the precedent in Beyoğlu; and the ghost ship of Darzanà (Baştarda) was re-constructed in the elongated volume of an archetypal space, on the shores of Goldenhorn. YKKS is both a transformation and preservation project with the radical interference towards an existing building. The memory of space was produced with a critical approach as the emergent atrium both separates and connects two worlds: the building and the city, the new and the old, the past and the present.

Baştarda is a transcultural and timeless vessel that was built from discarded objects found in an abandoned Tersane in İstanbul, later to be exhibited in an Arsenale in Venice. The memory of space was re-produced in an archetypal womb of a shipshed, in which an iterative confrontation of two cities occurs.

ykks.

The rationalist building of German architect Paul Schmitthenner, Beyoğlu 1960s.

Preliminary sketches of YKKS: Opening the façade towards the urban square through an atrium while preserving the three-dimensional structural grid of the existing building.

Conceptual model of the transformation: New and old building

existing building

side façades are reinforced inner structures are demolished

interior structures are rebuilt front façade is demolished

two steel pillars are built connected at the top with steel truss

slabs are connected through stairs

front glass façade is rebuilt

Diagram of the construction phases

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Photographs from the construction: Preservation, demolition and construction, all at once.

The emergent space (atrium) at the front became the confrontation area of both the old and new building with the city. Photograph: Ekin Özbiçer

darzanà.

Darzanà is a project which confronts two cities –Istanbul and Venice– both different and identical through a shared geography. A vessel, Baştarda, was built with the abandoned and discarded objects found in the Haliç shipyard.

Abandoned Objects in the Haliç Shipyard. More than 500 pieces of wooden moulds, furniture, signboards and boats are examined and collected. Photographs: Cemal Emden

MEMORY (RE)PRODUCED: YKKS AND DARZANĂ

Each piece was measured and modelled; suspended from a steel structure mounted on the ceiling. It was first constructed in Tersane and then re-constructed in Arsenal.

memory (re)produced.

Baştarda in Tersane, İstanbul. Photograph: Cemal Emden

Schmitthenner Building, 2010s Photograph: Cemal Emden

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Baştarda in Arsenale, Venice. Photograph: Cemal Emden
The shipsheds of Istanbul and Venice looked at each other through a hybrid ship that comes from the future; carrying the memories and telling stories of two cultures.

YKKS Building, 2017. Photograph: Cemal Emden
Rather than a replica without a past, a new structure encountering with its past self from within, was produced.

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Rue des Palais 153 - 1030 Brussels
T. +32 (0)2 244 44 35
info@architectureinpractice.eu
www.architectureinpractice.eu/pirjournal

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